

An Iterated Function System for Reich Contraction in Complete B-Metric Space

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Abstract : In this paper, we introduce R-Iterated Function System and employ the Hutchinson Barnsley theory (HB) to construct a fractal set as its unique fixed point by using Reich contractions in a complete b-metric space. We discuss about well-posedness of fixed point problem for b-metric space.

Keywords : fractals, iterated function system, compact set, reich contraction, well-posedness

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